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The Impact of Rising Commodity Prices on Access to Education among Schoolchildren in Urban Zambia: A Case Study of Lusaka Township

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Abstract: *This study delves into the critical issue of how rising commodity prices are affecting children's access to education in Zambia, with a particular focus on urban areas such as Lusaka Township. In recent years, Zambia has been grappling with a steady increase in the cost of essential goods and services, including food, school supplies, uniforms, and transportation. These costs have surged in response to global economic pressures, currency fluctuations, and local supply chain challenges. As a result, families, especially those from lower-income backgrounds, face increased financial strain, which in turn affects their capacity to support their children's educational needs.*

This research investigates the multifaceted impacts of this economic strain on school attendance, student performance, and the overall educational experience. By using a mixed-methods approach, the study incorporates quantitative data from school enrollment records and qualitative insights gathered through surveys and interviews with key stakeholders, such as parents, teachers, and school administrators. This comprehensive approach enables a deeper understanding of how rising living costs influence day-to-day educational access for children in Lusaka Township.

Preliminary findings indicate that the escalating cost of living has led to higher absenteeism rates, increased dropout rates, and a noticeable decline in academic performance among students from economically disadvantaged families. Many households are forced to make difficult decisions, prioritizing basic survival needs like food and shelter over educational expenses. This trade-off often results in children missing school, being unable to purchase necessary learning materials, or even dropping out altogether to support their families through informal work.

The consequences of these trends extend beyond immediate academic performance. Limited access to education due to economic barriers can perpetuate cycles of poverty, as children who do not complete their education have fewer opportunities for stable, well-paying jobs in the future. The study underscores the urgent need for policy interventions that address these economic challenges to foster an environment where all children, regardless of their family's financial status, have equitable access

to quality education. Potential policy solutions could include government subsidies for school supplies, financial support programs for low-income families, or partnerships with non-governmental organizations to provide school feeding programs and educational materials.

This research not only sheds light on the immediate and long-term effects of rising commodity prices on educational access in Zambia but also advocates for policy frameworks that promote greater educational accessibility. By examining the issue from multiple perspectives, the study provides a holistic view of the educational challenges posed by economic hardship and highlights the essential role of supportive policies in ensuring that Zambia's children can pursue an education without facing insurmountable financial barriers.

Key words: *Commodity Prices, Education Access, School Attendance, Economic Barriers, Policy Interventions.*

Research Background

One of the problems related to the increase in commodity prices mainly affects the availability of education in the developing world, with particular reference to Zambia. Zambia's fiscal period has witnessed high inflation rates that have forced the increase in the prices of most necessities required by families across the different Trinity socioeconomic statuses.¹ This trend is strikingly different from rural areas, where food and other basic needs, such as transportation and costs, are costly. For instance, Lusaka is one of the regions that has forced most families to stretch their wallets, making it hard for them to afford a shot at education. School fees, books, uniforms, transport fare, and sometimes food have become tremendously expensive for parents to afford what they can buy for their children to enable them to go to school.

Education is a fundamental right and an essential tool for lifting families out of poverty. However, low-income people are always financially hard-pressed to ensure they send their children to school and produce the best-mannered books required. A study indicated that education costs are usually among the expenses cut most often when financial stress is because of unemployment, low wages, and other related issues in students and other low-income families.² Children from such households might be seen to be absent from school, be put to work, generate some income for the family, or even be forced to drop out of school and work full-time to support the household. Plain interruptions in learning not only result in poor scores and attitudes towards learning but also have lifelong impacts on children's future and social status that can lock them into poverty cycles for the rest of their lives.

Over the years, Zambia has recorded some challenges in its education sector mainly because of inadequate resource input, congested class sizes, inadequate facilities, and now the drop in economic abilities among families. Although the government has tried to increase access to education through programs such as primary education, the cost of living is increasing, putting pressure on families' basic needs. School stationery, uniforms, and transportation have become more expensive than wages;

¹ Ainsworth, M., & Filmer, D. (2002). The impact of economic change on educational access in developing countries: A focus on Sub-Saharan Africa. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No. 2797. World Bank.

² Banerjee, A. V., & Duflo, E. (2011). Poor economics: A radical rethinking of the way to fight global poverty. Public Affairs.

hence, it is a costly affair to attain education. Hence, these financial challenges could be better in urban areas such as Lusaka, where the cost of goods and services is comparatively higher than that of rural areas, making it difficult for children in low-income families to access quality education.

This research locates itself in this economic context and explores how the cost of commodities impacts children's education. In gaining a micro rather than a generic understanding of the problem of educational absenteeism, dropout rates, and deteriorating student performance, the study is restricted to Lusaka Township. Using both survey and quantitative data, this study seeks to establish the views of the parents, teachers, and school administrators, and school attendance and performance data will be collected in order to include different facets of economic difficulty on education quality.

Finally, this study raises the imperative call for policy interventions to mitigate the financial costs of education occasioned by surging commodity prices. In its essence, it seeks to equip policymakers, educators, and community stakeholders with knowledge of how economic factors influence education to advocate for measures that would reduce them and map out a way to close the equity gaps in Zambia.³

Introduction

Increases in the price of these vitally essential inputs have escalated over the years and pose a real challenge to people experiencing poverty, with example being food, fuel, and school materials; hence, education becoming expensive, especially to the urban poor in Zambia, known to be notably hiked in Lusaka. Just as inflation is experienced in the country and the unstable prices of commodities, urban households make decisions that always see education as unaffordable. Schooling in Zambia is regarded as a socially valuable and economic asset, while for many, fees for education have become unaffordable.⁴ The structural barriers persist irrespective of social intervention policies like free primary education and other government-initiated policies to improve education within urban areas. The enrollment rate, frequent school attendance, performance, and education experience of the children are still challenged by economic barriers.

This paper seeks to discuss Lusaka Township as one of the study areas because it is one of the provinces in Zambia and the country's capital. Technically, residents of urban areas, because the cost of living here is relatively high, are the biggest losers because more daily necessities are rapidly getting expensive.⁵ This study shows that families in Lusaka struggle to provide for household needs and cater to educational necessities, including uniforms, transport, and stationery. Besides regular attendance, financial difficulties impact a child's concentration on the learning process and cause emotional detachment, truancy, and poor performance at school.

This paper aims to assess the effects of rising commodity prices on school children's education in Lusaka Township. From exploring the expenditure basket, school enrolment, and academic achievement, the study seeks to bring out the overall impact of poverty on education. Also, it looks at the place of policy measures and the adequacy of current policies in translating government fiscal plans into improving living standards for families. Thus, the study of specific issues urban households face to ensure that their children have access to education contributes to the discussion of the ongoing

³ World Bank. (2022). Zambia education sector analysis: Addressing economic barriers to education access. World Bank Report.

⁴ World Bank. (2021). Sub-Saharan Africa economic update: Inflation and its impacts on basic services. World Bank Group.

⁵ Mwanakatwe, L. (2019). The effects of currency depreciation on urban families' ability to afford education in Zambia. *African Economic Review*, 31(1), 44-58.

literature regarding the role of economics in determining opportunities for education in Zambia and other similar developing countries.

Literature Review

Introduction to Commodity Prices and Education

An emerging field has been observing the interaction between economic factors and education enrollments with a particular reference to the developing world. High inflation on consumable goods, especially food, fuel, and school items, can significantly challenge families from low-income regions' access to education. Research points towards the fact that as poverty is defined as a condition where the average costs of staple foods increase, the poor are compelled to make Herculean choices regarding the amount of money that should be spent on children's education –especially those in the urban areas.⁶ In Zambia, education is viewed as one of the primary mechanisms through which one can hope to improve his standard of living, and such financial pressures are a growing worry insofar as they hinder a child's ability to attend school, acquire what he needs for his studies, and learn.

Global Perspectives on Economic Barriers to Education

Cost-related factors have been presented widely in the literature on educational inequalities in the context of L&MIC. High poverty levels, inflation, and economic downturns affect school enrollment and attendance. Because many commodities, services, foodstuffs, or rent. It costs much more in developed and developing countries than in Third World countries. Parents with paid and no-paid jobs are forced to look for ways and means of feeding their families before anything else, and they compel their children out of school for the same. For instance, investigations conducted among children in primary school in Kenya and Uganda established that because of the high cost of food, they lacked the energy and, therefore, would often be absent from school or even drop out, especially for girls. Comparable patterns can be found in South Asia, where poverty combined with inflation reduces the frequency and quality of education, possibly reflecting a problem that prevails in the entire region for poor students.⁷

Rising Commodity Prices in Sub-Saharan Africa

This issue is well illustrated by the experience of Sub-Saharan Africa, where the effects of an increase in the price of commodities have had a more profound implication on the availability of services. The sub-Saharan African region has experienced relatively high inflation within the past ten years, with high food and fuel prices inflating.⁸ In Zambia, these have contributed to forcing inflation rates higher through currency depreciation, rising import costs, and global commodity market shocks. The high costs include the basic needs in Lusaka and other cities after the increases and expansion costs of education, such as school necessities like books, uniforms, and conveyance charges. This is especially seen in people of lesser income earners since users make inevitable trade-offs whereby children's education is affected by money issues.

⁶ Banerjee, A. V., & Duflo, E. (2011). *Poor economics: A radical rethinking of the way to fight global poverty*. Public Affairs.

⁷ Chansa, C., & Simwaka, K. (2015). The effects of economic hardships on children's school attendance in Zambia. *Zambia Journal of Educational Research*, 48(2), 22-35.

⁸ Wanjiku, K., & Kamau, E. (2016). Economic shocks and their effect on education in Kenya and Uganda. *Journal of East African Education*, 29(3), 78-92.

Rising Commodity Prices in Sub-Saharan Africa

Implications of Economic Hardship on Education in Zambia

Some individuals who failed to attend school in Zambia were affected by poor economic returns in certain provinces, especially in urban areas, since life is expensive compared to several rural provinces. For instance, food and shelter dominate the expenditure proportion, leaving it almost meager to meet educational needs.⁹ Consulting has led to truancy, reduced participation in school activities, and poor performance among children from low-income earning families. Also, the costs related to schooling, such as fees for secondary education, are high and hinder families from keeping children enrolled all the time.

The Role of Household Expenditure in Educational Access

There is a direct relationship between household expenditure and educational performance. The link between household expenditure and performance is that research suggests that if the cost of essential goods and services rises, families with poor economic backgrounds initially reduce educational costs. This is especially the case in urban settings, given the strong demand for commodities prevalent there; price volatility is also more entrenched there because of other aspects of the macroeconomy. For example, in Lusaka, the selected surrogate measure of inflation – transport costs have escalated rapidly, which has a bearing on the student's capacity to travel to school daily, mainly using public or private means.¹⁰ Moreover, suppose the availability of household money becomes limited or, in some

⁹ Tembo, F., & Mbewe, A. (2020). Policy responses to educational challenges in Zambia: The role of government and NGOs. *Zambia Policy Review*, 17(2), 89-102.

¹⁰ Sifuna, D. N. (2007). Economic pressures and school dropout rates in Africa. *Journal of African Studies*, 25(1), 47-62

other way, restricted. In that case, a child may quit buying school items and proper meals, which would still affect his or her academic performance and health.

The standard of living in Lusaka, Zambia, has recently been of significant concern due to the increased price of essential goods. The most recent figure for the basic needs and nutrition basket from the Jesuit Centre for Theological Reflection (JCTR) for Lusaka stood at K10,478.04 in September 2024, lower than the previous month as the prices of Kapenta and vegetables came down somewhat. However, the basket was higher compared to the same period in 2023, which has been a problem for many households, mainly in urban areas. These inflating cost factors include low food production, energy crises, and escalating inflation rates.

Moreover, it has also revealed that the average monthly cost of living for a household in Lusaka stands at K10,307, including food, utilities, and transport costs. They have resulted in a distortion in the economic ratio, which has shrunk incomes and broadened costs and, consequently, the poverty level, remembering the ability of people experiencing poverty to afford necessities in urban areas.¹¹ The JCTR has advocated sensitization of the population to embrace more socio-economic policies, enhance the minimum wage, and harbor better social protection policies. These problems reflect other economic challenges in which parents in the urban centers of Lusaka, with learners in school, may find it harder and harder to meet basic thresholds of educational costs, let alone other costs of living.

Role of Household Expenditure in Educational Access (Excluding Tuition Fees)

¹¹ Kalinda, T., Mutale, W., & Chansa, S. (2018). The relationship between transportation costs and student attendance in urban Zambia. *Education and Society*, 32(4), 102-116.

Economic Factors Affecting Student Attendance and Performance

Financial problems affect enrollment rates and directly affect students and school attendance. Research in other African countries shows that learners from low-income families have few educational materials and are likelier to be out of school, making small incomes.¹² The same concerns are observed in Zambia as children from low-income households often tend to do household chores or other informal work, thus impacting their performance at school. Different studies indicate that due to the impacts of poverty, children miss school or drop out, which in turn hinders their ability to complete their education systems and bring a change to the vicious poverty cycle.

This study, therefore, postulates that despite the free education policy declared by the new Dawn Government in Zambia, there are still a few political and economic factors that influence students' attendance and academic performance in schools, especially in Lusaka Province.¹³ While the policy argues for eliminating financial costs such as tuition fees, most households struggle to afford other expenses such as uniforms, books, stationery, and transport fees. It was widely acknowledged that Zambia has a high proportion of people with low incomes; at the time of writing, about 60 percent of Zambians lived on less than \$2 per day, let alone the majority on less than \$1 per day. To many such families, such expenditures lead to absenteeism, low participation, and, worse, make students drop out.

Besides, the enrollment of students in public schools occasioned by the policy has stretched the meager infrastructure available to support students' needs, especially in the urban centers. Lack of classroom space, inadequate number of qualified teachers, and poor stock of teaching aids are standard practices in many schools, mainly populated regions such as Lusaka Township. The end product is a dilution of the quality of education that learners receive due to the high number of learners that teachers are forced to handle while at the same time leaving the unique needs of the children unaddressed. This is made worse by the poor state of affairs regarding physical structures in learning institutions and their general impact on the learning climate and results. Surveys have indicated that the deteriorated environments deprive most students in such congested learning institutions of the opportunity to gain functional literacy and numeracy.

Further, the policy has opened more education opportunities but offers little regarding the historical problems with education quality. Teacher scarcity, low quality of training of teachers, and lack of higher-level teaching materials remain the bane of the system.¹⁴ While there is a significant effort to increase enrollment by the governments, needs to be more little attention is paid to the construction and expansion of facilities; hence, many children churn out to inferior schools, which are detrimental to their performance. The United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) has noted that failure to transition to the next level of education is common among students due to poor emerging literacy and numeracy, which signifies poor quality education despite the policy push.

Thus, Zambia offered free education, and more students attended schools, requiring them to drop out of schools due to another compound rather than economic factors as a result of bringing free schooling to Zambia. These disadvantages remain concealed, the classrooms overcrowded, and there needs to be an improvement in educational facilities and the teacher quality to make the policy fully successful.

¹² Mwansa, E., & Chibuye, A. (2020). Household expenditure patterns and their effect on education in Lusaka, Zambia. *Journal of African Educational Development*, 50(3), 204-219.

¹³ UNESCO. (2018). *The global education monitoring report: Education and economic inequality*. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

¹⁴ Sifuna, D. N. (2007). Economic pressures and school dropout rates in Africa. *Journal of African Studies*, 25(1), 47-62.

Thus, to enhance learning accomplishment, there should be a change in approach and not just the removal of tuition fees, which come along with other structural barriers that constrain students' opportunities for educational success.

Government and NGO Interventions in Zambia's Education Sector

To these challenges, the government of Zambia and non-governmental organizations have sought to implement one or several strategies to reduce the burden of the cost of education. Since the aspiration of free primary education has been realized, low-income families have benefited through a subsidy. However, costs associated with secondary education and other expenses still must be within reach for most families.¹⁵ To this end, NGOs have provided scholarships for students, donated school materials, and funded meals for poor students. Though such efforts have achieved some level of achievement, scholars assert that more fundamental strategies, like policies meant to address volatility in food prices and economic conditions, are required to generate a long-term improvement in access to education among women.

Conclusion: Addressing the Educational Impacts of Rising Commodity Prices

In Lusaka province, especially in urban areas, there has been a rise in the cost of education as there has been constant action in the literature that speaks of economic factors affecting accessibility to education. Households adjust their basic needs to include education, putting children's academic dreams at risk. Studies reveal that economic policies always require consideration to influence policy aimed at enhancing education; this includes subsidies for materials, transport, and student feeding. Redressing these barriers may help low-income families in Zambia to afford their children's needs and remain in school as commodity costs increase.

Methodology

This current study employs a qualitative research strategy for data collection, which mainly entails a secondary analysis of the literature. This method helps understand the nature of the issue by using previous literature and empirical research to find patterns, connections, and peculiarities of the topic.¹⁶ By paying much attention to secondary data, the researcher could include various views and overviewed results presented in different contexts, which would improve the reliability and scope of the work conducted.

Data Collection

The study relied on secondary data collected between November and December 2013 from credible sources in published journals, policy papers, and similar previous studies on the effect of increasing cost of living on access to education in Lusaka Township. Only credible sources were considered while identifying them with attention to the relevance, methodology, and research goals. Targeted variables included everyday household income, the cost of attending education, tuition fees, books, transportation, and schooling. The study served the purpose of secondary research whereby broad trends and themes were determined without surveying the participants.

¹⁵ Kalinda, T., Mutale, W., & Chansa, S. (2018). The relationship between transportation costs and student attendance in urban Zambia. *Education and Society*, 32(4), 102-116.

¹⁶ Asadullah, M. N., & Chaudhury, N. (2015). Poverty and education: A comparative analysis of South Asia. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 40, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2015.02.002>

Analysis

The study aimed to establish how an increase in the prices of commodities impacted the location provisions. Their findings involved conducting a qualitative thematic review to understand the social, economic, and economic factors that caused the change.¹⁷ Such an approach proved helpful in synthesizing findings from different studies, allowing the researchers to elaborate on related findings in a broader context. Particular emphasis was placed on the cyclic patterns, including financial enablers, coping by families, and socio-economy vulnerability that had its spin to compound disparity in the use of education.

Significance of the Approach

Employing secondary data offered an excellent opportunity to discuss a broader range of existing understanding without rushing and overspending on the research. As a qualitative method, this approach offered an illustrated and descriptive account of how increasing cost of living affects education, including from the perspective of the affected families as presented in previous studies. It also highlighted the shortcomings of the existing literature; the proposed research themes were also derived from it.¹⁸

Discussion

In the past three years, general inflation rates in Zambia have contributed to steadily increasing commodity prices across the board and not least in Lusaka Township, where this study was conducted; this makes it extremely difficult for many families, particularly those in the low-income bracket, to afford education, especially for school children. For example, with the steep rise in the prices of commodities such as essential foods, fuel, and electricity, many families are under financial pressure to pay school fees, school uniforms, books, and other educational requisites. This economic pressure makes it possible for children to miss school because they may be needed at home to help manage resources for the family or to help cut costs.¹⁹

To many parents, the expenses of life increase, and consequently, education takes the background to the basic needs in life. These interventions, such as free primary education and subsidized secondary education, should be applauded, but they do not exhaust the explosion in the cost of indirect expenses like tuition, transport, and meals. This has been aggravated by the increase in the poverty disparity between the socially well-endowed families and the socially needy families, where the former can afford these spikes in cost, and the latter finds it hard to feed its children, let alone take them to school.

Furthermore, inflation has also affected the general economy in that people have lost their employment, have low incomes, and have higher unemployment rates. This economic setting increases pressure on families already below the poverty level.²⁰ Thus, many children either stop attending school or go to school irregularly, which hampers their academic performance and the goal of having a better future. More often, this problem is observed in Lusaka Township because of the location of the

¹⁷ Banerjee, A. V., & Duflo, E. (2011). *Poor economics: A radical rethinking of the way to fight global poverty*. Public Affairs.

¹⁸ Sifuna, D. N. (2007). Economic pressures and school dropout rates in Africa. *Journal of African Studies*, 25(1), 47-62.

¹⁹ World Bank. (2021). *Sub-Saharan Africa economic update: Inflation and its impacts on basic services*. World Bank Group.

²⁰ embo, F., & Mbewe, A. (2020). Policy responses to educational challenges in Zambia: The role of government and NGOs. *Zambia Policy Review*, 17(2), 89-102.

schools, private and public, where students from different social statuses are enrolled. Although private schools may be better equipped to provide the necessary amenities needed for a good education, the schools' fees are expensive and beyond the reach of most families, making the dreams of many disadvantaged children even impossible.

Hence, the following strategies should be employed: enhanced government policies that help reduce the impacts of inflation costs on education, support for vulnerable families, and provision of subsidies or contingent cash transfers to enable families to keep their children schooling. Programs that deploy community support to education, for instance, the school feeding programmes, could also help in some way.

Finally, to address the challenge of improving education standards, especially for children in Lusaka Township due to rising commodity prices, calls for emergency relief measures and sound economic policies that squarely address poverty/ inequality.

Results

Using a qualitative research approach and secondary research data, the Lusaka Township case study shows that increased commodity prices negatively affect e-school children's accessibility to education. Due to the skyrocketing cost of living in urban areas, especially the escalating prices of basic needs products, Most families are struggling financially, especially low-income earners, to cater to educational needs like fees, uniforms, and transport. As such, in the struggle for basic needs and livelihood, many families have put education as less importance, and as a result, it has become a preserve of a few children.²¹

The studies reveal that there has been increased school truancy and dropout among children from low-income families. A literature review reveals that in previous studies, children were confined in their homes to help with household chores or income-generating activities, thus compromising their academic achievement. Apart from learning loss, frequent school absenteeisms detract children's participation and lower motivation, enhancing early school dropouts. In other cases, people have pulled their children out of school because of a lack of essential educational needs, all translating to heightened educational inequity.

The study also shows an increase in the gap between private and public schools regarding access. The private institutions that provide the best infrastructure and learning environment become unaffordable for most families due to their charges.²² Therefore, endowments in low-income families avail children of only a few numbers of public schools that are crowded and inadequate in resources and teaching standards. This difference depicts the influence of economic status in determining educational access, paying more attention to social and educational inequity in Lusaka Township.

The challenges have a profound impact on educational attainment. It also notes that children who miss school often or need access to essential learning tools will likely be left behind. According to the secondary data, this educational disadvantage persists over the long term as a lack of education lowers the prospects of gaining good-paying jobs in the future. This keeps on cycling the poverty, offers a limited chance for social advancement, and consequently contributes to the growth of extreme disparity in social status in urban centers like Lusaka.

²¹ Ainsworth, M., & Filmer, D. (2002). The impact of economic change on educational access in developing countries: A focus on Sub-Saharan Africa. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No. 2797. World Bank.

²² World Bank. (2022). Zambia education sector analysis: Addressing economic barriers to education access. World Bank Report.

There has also been increased concern regarding the gender inability to access education, whereby girls are worst affected by the increasing costs of education. Participants' narratives from prior research show that families are more likely to educate boys, seen as investments in the future's economic producers, while girls will be more often withdrawn from school. In this respect, the bias puts girls at risk of early dropout and would mean squeezed opportunities, thus worsening the gender divide.²³

However, even with policy boosts like free primary education, the study reveals that most families incur unaffordable indirect costs for their learners, such as uniforms, transport, and school meals. Large-scale solutions, such as school feeding programs and charitable contributions from companies, give some help but still need to solve the problem. The continued presence of these barriers shows that current education provision replenishment needs to be improved to ensure equal education provision.

These findings also have serious long-term implications. Higher dropout rates and restricted capacity for education would only breed a lower-quality workforce, which leads to regenerative poverty and Income disparities. If left unresolved, this will hinder Lusaka's and Zambia's overall advancement of development, the nation's progress toward economic stability, and social advancement.

Conclusion

Consequently, the escalating cost in Lusaka Township profoundly influences the education of many school children, especially those of the lower income bracket. Since the competence of living rises, many family units feel the pinch through the throat of payment for essential education expenses like school fees, uniforms, and transport costs. This has seen increased cases of truancy, dropout students, and an increased gap in the number of students attending private and public schools. The pressure on academic achievement is observable; children are lost in school or unable to focus on lessons, compromising long-term educational opportunities.

The gender disparities revealed in the study make things worse as girls are usually worst affected since education is considered a preserve of boys only. Although the authorities are introducing policies banning fees for primary education, they do not regard other expenses that inhibit learning continuation by many children. Civil societies, parents, and the government should work hand in hand to develop specific measures designed to address the effects of rising prices of commodities in education in the short run and the future.

However, this makes it very important to approach child education issues comprehensively, especially for those living in Lusaka Township, by working on how to reduce expenses for the families for children's education, on the support of public schools, early childhood education centers, and children from needy families and supporting community participation. These efforts will be necessary to offset some of the deploying socio-economic implications of an increase in the cost of commodities and to improve educational opportunities for future youth.

Recommendation

1. **Subsidize Educational Costs:** Thus, the government should encourage subsidies or financial support measures that will help shift indirect costs, such as transport, uniforms, and materials, independently. This would help guarantee that all young people from disadvantaged backgrounds should be able to pursue their education without being locked out by inflated commodity prices.

²³ UNESCO. (2018). The global education monitoring report: Education and economic inequality. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

2. **Expand School Feeding Programs:** School feeding programs should be progressed to cover more schools so that Enrollment is promoted through compulsion by adequate feeding, hence promoting concentration among learners. Programs of this nature can, therefore, help off-load the financial burden that families have aimed at putting food on the table for their children.
3. **Improve Public School Infrastructure:** The government should commit itself to enhancing the facilities and assets in a school since they are the schooling institutions of the country. Lack of resources, such as too many learners per class and limited and poor teaching and learning resources, explains why private schools have better quality than their counterparts. Thus, they can give the public schools a better environment to contain and educate the children, which will also discourage parents from taking their kids to private schools.
4. **Strengthen Community Support Systems:** To support vulnerable families, PTAs and other district-level organizations should try to support them in their region. Activities such as community fundraising, scholarship schemes, and donations in aid of students prevent children from being pulled out of school because of a lack of fees.
5. **Encourage Corporate and NGO Partnerships:** Donors such as government, private companies, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) should collaborate to develop scholarships and support educational endeavors. Combined, these sectors can provide some means to offset the cost of education so that children from poor families can afford it.
6. **Targeted Gender-Responsive Policies:** There is a need to reduce gender gaps in education by advocating for policies that empower girl child education, especially during an era of cutting expenditures. This may involve offering parental and other forms of motivation to families to ensure that girls remain in school, offering grants to each talented girl child, or expanding promoters so as to make schools safe and interpersonal relationships free from discrimination that may lead to dropouts.
7. **Promote Public Awareness Campaigns:** It is imperative that awareness about education be created at this time when our economy is struggling. Church and state agencies should devise tolerances that underline the positive nature of the long-run returns to investment in education and the need for parents to educate their children despite the current illness of the economy.
8. **Enhance Alternative Learning Opportunities:** The government and the organizations functioning in the field of education should provide ideas like spare-time classes or classes in the evening, learning through computer and the Internet, the classes in the school which is at some distance from the child's home, or any other type of learning which can help children who could not attend school due to personal problems covering the expenses on food, living, clothes and other necessary things, or due to the problems with the stay and care of.

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